

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TRINIDAD MAYA****FIRST NAME: PERLA GIOVANNA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is <18%

The author used the following software: Windows 11

List your seven key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-12)
2. Punctuations: Use of Comma (EUCLID 2021, 19)
3. Plagiarism: (EUCLID 2021, 33-36)
4. Styling Guide: (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. The Chicago Manual of Style (CMOS), Footnotes and Endnotes (EUCLID 2021, 52-54)
6. Latin Abbreviations and Their Common Mistakes (EUCLID 2021, 58-60)
7. Does and Don'ts of Writing a Response Paper: The Conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 65-72)

“WHAT ARE THE MOST COMMON WRITING ERRORS WE SHOULD AVOID IN IMPROVING OUR ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING?”

1) INTRODUCTION

The following essay aims to demonstrate my interaction, analysis, and reflection on the concepts learned in the ACA-401D course, period one, using the book entitled “ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1” along with the course videos. The chosen topic for discussion is “What are the most common writing errors we should avoid in improving our academic essay writing?”

2) WHAT IS AN ACADEMIC ESSAY AND WHAT ARE ITS BASIC CHARACTERISTICS?

The most crucial aspect of avoiding errors in academic essay writing is a clear definition that allows us to understand its scope, components, and differences from other forms of writing.

In this regard, we can define the academic essay as a complex discursive genre within the argumentative textual typology (Zambrano 2012, 6). It is a research work written through judgment, reflection, and analysis of a specific topic (Mejía 2018, 3). An academic essay provides answers for the hypotheses we formulate and helps us resolve them through evidence (EUCLID 2021, 7).

When discussing an academic essay, it is essential to distinguish it from a literary essay, as this guides its correct development.

Thus, we can highlight that literary essays have a more aesthetic and creative purpose, emphasizing the manner and originality of writing, unlike academic essays, where the topics must always maintain a level of formality that allows the author to demonstrate their hypothesis or stance through an argumentative sequence (UAM-A 2016, 1).

Now that we have a clearer understanding of the definition of an academic essay and its differentiation from other writings, it is also necessary to comprehend its components to avoid errors during its writing process.

An essay always includes an introduction, a body, and a conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10). The introduction involves selecting a specific idea that constitutes a response to a question. This section should be at most one paragraph and contain the following parts: First, a brief general introduction to the topic. Second is the thesis, which indicates the interpretation of the implications of the question and the order that the essay will follow (Gamboa 1997, 3).

The body of the essay can be described as the point where you respond to your question and support your argument with evidence, developing an organized and structured discussion where you demonstrate your knowledge and understanding of the topic (Euclid 2021, 10).

Finally, in a resume, it is necessary to restate the question and compile the most important points (EUCLID 2021, 10). Its purpose is to engage in an abstraction exercise of all ideas and provide a resolution to the posed hypothesis.

Up to this point, we could conclude that the most common errors arise from not being able to initially understand what an essay is, how it differs from other texts, and what its components are—definitions that form the basis for obtaining adequate development of an academic essay and avoiding errors in writing. Next, we will delve further into the specific errors of the seven critical concepts selected for this essay.

a) PUNCTUATION ERRORS

The first key concept we will analyze is punctuation, which is one of the most common errors when drafting an academic essay. To do so, briefly describing what we mean by punctuation errors is necessary. In practical terms, these need to be improved in syntactic-semantic segmentations that detract from the clarity and communicative effectiveness of the text, deviating from norms (Raventos 2012, 349).

However, what types of common errors do we find in punctuation? One of the most common errors among students is related to punctuation rules, including omission, improper placement, and overuse (Horadeestudio 2017, 7). For instance, a study analyzing the most common punctuation errors among thirty-eight first-year university students with an average age of nineteen revealed that the most prominent error was the absence of a comma following a clausal modifier. Among the thirty-seven subjects who used these indicators, twenty-two did not use a comma, accounting for 59% (Raventos 2012, 351).

We could argue that the comma is the punctuation mark par excellence that accounts for the most incorrect uses (Rodríguez Muñoz and Ridao Rodrigo 2013, 13). As mentioned in our Course pack: Period 1, commas should be used to add information without altering the sentence's meaning and thus avoid this typical error (EUCLID 2021, 19).

b) PLAGIARISM IS THE MOST SERIOUS ERROR OF ALL

For the most common errors in academic writing, it is paramount to mention that the most severe error is plagiarism due to its ethical consequences, respect for readers, and legal ramifications.

However, what is plagiarism, and how can it be avoided? An unequivocal and concise definition of plagiarism is as follows: When you take any information from another author without crediting their idea and use it as if it were your intellectual property (EUCLID 2021, 34).

There are various alternatives outlined in the literature to avoid plagiarism. For example, one study focuses on previous research on plagiarism and academic misconduct between 2009 and 2018. The study is a systematic review based on 408 sample records from the Scopus database. It also identifies strategies to avoid plagiarism, such as using highlighted text in quotation marks, utilizing anti-plagiarism software, and adopting a zero-tolerance policy against such activities (Awasthi 2019, 98).

As the final strategies to implement to avoid plagiarism, one should always use one's own words, paraphrase the ideas produced by an author, and consistently cite the sources from which information one took (EUCLID 2021, 36).

i) *UNDERSTANDING THE STYLE GUIDE AND THE CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE TO AVOID ERRORS WHEN WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY*

A style guide is a system that enables you to write coherently and avoid errors by providing a way to document basic rules or features of your writing to ensure consistency in your written output (EUCLID 2021, 41).

The Chicago Manual of Style is the respected, time-honored style guide favored by history and science publications and university departments (Roberta et al. 1998, 6). It states that any idea or text not of the author's own should be cited appropriately. This rule applies through direct quotations or paraphrasing (Zamora and Osorio 2020, 27).

There are two central systems for crediting or documenting information from sources: the footnote or endnote system and the in-text or parenthetical system (Roberta F. et al. 1998, 6). Chicago employs two systems to document sources used in work: the first is the notes system, which uses footnotes and a bibliography, and the author-date system, where the author's name and publication date are inserted in parentheses in the text, correlating with the reference list (Zamora and Osorio 2020, 28).

Although both systems convey all the essential information about each source, they differ not only in how they direct readers to these sources but also in terms of their format, which can lead to errors such as improper placement of dates in citation entries or incorrect ordering.

The style guide encompasses many necessary elements to avoid errors in daily work (EUCLID 2021, 42). Finally, due to the quantity and detail of these elements, the importance of adhering to a single style guide is emphasized.

ii) *THE CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE (CMS), ERRORS IN FOOTNOTES AND ENDNOTES*

We quote from the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) because it has become a standard reference for students worldwide. The guidelines in this manual offer practical solutions to a wide range of issues encountered (EUCLID 2021, 44).

The Chicago Manual of Style explains that endnotes and footnotes are valuable tools for enriching essay writing. For this reason, it is essential to understand and differentiate between them to avoid errors.

In this regard, we consider footnotes as auxiliary discourse serving the text, an effective brief form that continues the narrative flow and allows the reader to explore additional, tangential information at the narrative's edge (Zwanck 2019, 2).

As the name implies, footnotes are placed at the bottom of the page, while endnotes are placed at the end of a chapter or at the end of a written paper (SBFCA 1 Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México 2025, 1).

Finally, to avoid the most common errors when citing, all Chicago notes should be placed in the order in which they are cited and should be consistent with the collocation style.

Furthermore, always include the bibliography on the paper when using footnotes. Including the bibliography is an obligation that allows the reader to find a source readily.

iii) *THE MEANING OF LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND THEIR COMMON MISTAKES*

Latin abbreviations allow us to express or identify situations in bibliographic citations that make references shorter (Sierra Rodríguez 2010, 17).

There is a reason these abbreviations still survive and are still used today: They contain much meaning in a tiny package (University of North Carolina, n.d., 1).

Currently, three well-known Latin abbreviations are the most often misused: etcetera., i.e., and, e.g.,. Within these, e.g., and, i.e., are the two most often misused and confused Latin abbreviations (University of North Carolina n.d., 2).

The abbreviation, for example, (e.g.), in Latin has the meaning of *exempli gratia*. When you use, e.g., you should provide one or two short examples to help clarify the preceding idea, but they should be simple and expressed in a single word or short phrase (University of North Carolina n.d, 3).

For the abbreviation, i.e., in Latin, it is “*id est*,” and the meaning in English is “that is” (EUCLID 2021, 60). Both should appear in parentheses and offer additional information to help explain what was written earlier. However, remember that, i.e., stands for a strict equivalence, unlike, e.g., which is used to give an example or set of examples to help clarify the preceding idea (University of North Carolina n.d., 3).

Finally, for the Latin abbreviation, etc., in Latin, it is “*et cetera*,” and the meaning in English is “and so on; and other people/things” (EUCLID 2021, 60). It is used at the end of a list to indicate more elements (University of North Carolina n.d., 2).

3) CONCLUSION

I have always known that drafting an essay is not an easy labor, and it requires deep reflection and a solid commitment to the reader, as well as having the right tools to accomplish this arduous task. With this premise in mind, I began to interact with the course material and watch the videos. However, after taking a global look at the content, my first impression was that I needed more skill and experience to author an essay correctly.

Nevertheless, this feeling of helplessness in not being able to write an essay correctly generated many doubts that gave me the basis to continue researching and helping me write. Some of these doubts were: What is the importance of an essay? What are the types of essays that exist? Why does an essay require a style when writing it? How can we avoid problems when authoring an essay? It is for this reason that I chose the topic to investigate: What are the most common mistakes in writing that we should avoid to improve our academic essay writing? Because, as several authors point out, it is easier to learn from mistakes."

Finally, integrating the material learned and researching to resolve all these doubts, I began to realize that the most common mistakes can be summarized in these points:

The first is to understand what an academic essay is and its components, to understand that it is a text of the discursive genre that has a specific theme, structure, and style where, based on a hypothesis that we formulate, a response is sought through evidence and is planned based on argumentation. Additionally, it always maintains the following elements: an introduction, a body, and a conclusion.

The second point is to understand that punctuation errors are syntactic-semantic inadequacies that detract from the clarity and communicative effectiveness of the text and that, in this case, research showed us that the most frequent error was the absence of a comma after an adverbial clause.

The third, most important, and delicate point is to talk about the error of committing plagiarism: not giving credit to the author's idea and using it as if it were our own. This point is not only an error in writing but also an error that carries legal and ethical consequences. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to always cite any information that is not our own.

The fourth point that speaks to us about how a writing style documents basic rules or features of your writing to ensure consistency in your written output, in addition to mentioning The Chicago Manual of Style as one of the most used guides in history and science publications and departments in universities, to conclude with the importance of footnotes as an enriching resource in academic essays because it provides extra information to the reader that is on the edge of the narrative above.

The fifth and last point speaks to us about Latin abbreviations and that there is a reason these abbreviations have survived and continue to be used today: They contain much meaning in a tiny package. With this understanding, we must distinguish them as in the

case of, etc., i.e., e.g., where there are the most errors, and learning to recognize each one with its function guarantees us correct use.

After conducting this analysis, I still maintain that authoring an essay is challenging. However, now, with practice, reflection, and following the rules of adopting a style, it is less likely that I will make mistakes.

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